

Quality of Life in Oncology:
measuring what matters for
cancer patients and survivors
in Europe

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EUonQoL

Quality of Life in Oncology: measuring what matters for cancer
patients and survivors in Europe

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1. Introduction

Communication and dissemination are a core part of the EUonQoL project to ensure that project activities, resources and results are communicated to the relevant stakeholders in a clear, consistent, and effective manner.

The aim of this Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) is to outline the EUonQoL Communication Strategy, by analyzing the objectives of the EUonQoL project and tailoring a communication strategy geared towards maximizing the project impact; increasing its visibility; disseminating project advancements and ensuring result exploitation.

The structure of this Communication and Dissemination Plan consists of the following:

1. Project Background & Objectives – Where are we now?
2. Communication & Dissemination Objectives – What do we want to achieve?
3. Strategy – How do we get there?
4. Action Plan – What do we need to get there?
5. Quality Control – How do we monitor performance?

The EUonQoL Communication and Dissemination Plan should be understood as a living document. Accordingly, an updated version of the document will be published periodically to allow it to evolve over time, as a result of new or emerging information and opportunities.

2. Project Background & WP9 Outline

The improvement or preservation of quality of life (QoL) is one of the three pillars of the EC Mission on Cancer, which underpins the needs of patients from cancer diagnosis across treatment, survivorship, and advanced terminal stages of non-curable cases.

However, full implementation of QoL assessment in routine oncology practice is not yet part of standard of care and health care systems and cancer control programs do not take into consideration quality of life measures when devising clinical, societal, and healthcare policymaking systems.

The overall goal of **Quality of Life in Oncology: Measuring What Matters for Cancer Patients and Survivors in Europe (EUonQoL)** is therefore to be instrumental to the progress of the Mission on Cancer plan, as outlined in this project call, with the specific aim of developing, piloting, validating, and exploiting the European Oncology Quality of Life toolkit (EUonQoL-Kit) among European cancer patients and survivors.

It follows that EUonQoL has the following project objectives (POs):

- **PO1:** To identify gaps in the body of evidence and in currently available QoL assessment tools applied to European citizens with cancer as well as among cancer survivors;

- **PO2:** To develop an innovative, unified system for QoL assessment for cancer patients in different disease stages;
- **PO3:** To validate the EUonQoL-Kit in a pan European pilot survey;
- **PO4:** To provide preliminary estimates of QoL data and analyses of factors potentially associated to QoL in European patients and survivors;
- **PO5:** To develop procedures and actions aimed at establishing the basis for future monitoring of QoL in European cancer patients and survivors using the EUonQoL-Kit.

A dedicated WP9 - Dissemination and communication will implement the measures needed to maximise the impact of the project. WP9 is led by OECI and co-led by ECO. WP9 encompasses 5 tasks, as follows:

- *Task 9.1 Development and application of the dissemination and communication plan (Lead: OECI, contributors: ECO, Partners: INT, ALL) (M1-48)* This task will define, together with all partners, the strategic framework to maximize the impact and the visibility of the project among all relevant stakeholders and disseminate project advancements. A Dissemination and Communication Plan will identify the target audiences among patients and survivors, health care professionals, supportive workers and health authorities, policymakers. The appropriate channels, resources, and responsibilities will be defined in order to guarantee the development and maintenance of a website, the creation and publication of communication materials, and the definition of communication KPIs to measure the achievement of the objectives. A videoconference platform will be available for general meetings of the project and for discussions among the participants to each WP.
- *Task 9.2 Development and deployment of communication channels & materials (Lead: OECI, Contributors: ECO; Partners: All) (M1-48)* This task aims to design the project identity and develop the appropriate communication channels and materials to widely disseminate and communicate the project concept and potential benefits arising from its outcomes to the target groups (i.e. governments, patients' advocates and informal care-givers, patients' associations and public at large). To attain this goal, the following actions will be implemented: 1) developing the project brand via a) Branding activities (including logo), brochure/leaflet, newsletters, a biannual Edition of the OECI Magazine dedicated to the project. This activity will be supported by a subcontract with a graphic-designing agency with extensive expertise in the cancer area b) a website to be set-up by OECI in collaboration with a web developer with extensive expertise in the bio-medical field throughout the entire project. The website will feature a restricted area accessible via User ID and Password for all WP leaders. The latter will be required to utilise the Restricted Area to add reports; meeting agendas; scientific papers; WP mailing lists and other relevant information for the objectives of the project c) Social Media platforms, including LinkedIn/Facebook and Twitter to communicate news and outcomes to the lay public and relevant stakeholders. This activity will be assigned to ECO, which has extensive expertise creating a community of parties involved in the implementation and maintenance of better QoL conditions.

- *Task 9.3 Dissemination and outreach activities* (Lead: INT, Partners: ALL) (M1-M48) Project developments and results will be disseminated to the relevant audience using the tools and channels as per the communication plan. The website will be updated monthly and will provide information about the projects' objectives & approach, methodology, targets and partners, state of progress, public deliverables, publications, and events. The partners will produce peer-reviewed scientific papers of the relevant work packages to be submitted to dedicated Open Access journals. Throughout the project, scientific partners will share project results at scientific conferences. In addition, the OECI Oncology Days will host a dedicated session to present the state of play of some of the main projects related to the Mission on Cancer - including this one related to QoL - every year. The Final Conference of the project will be proposed as the main Scientific Conference of the OECI Oncology Days 2026 with the possibility to propose a Satellite Symposium converging all the main outcomes of the activities supported as part of the Mission on Cancer.
- *Task 9.4 Implementation of open science practices* (Lead: INT, Partners: ALL) (M1-48) To increase the transparency and accessibility of scientific research, we will implement open science practices under the premise "as open as possible as closed as necessary" to comply with IPR management, in particular: a) providing information about the research outputs/tools/instruments needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications or to validate/re-use research data; b) ensuring responsible management of research data ; c) sharing the project's results through open access scientific publications; d) digital or physical access to the results needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications.
- *Task 9.5. Policy outreach and dissemination* (Lead ECO, Participants: OECI, FAVO, APOZ, FABC) (M18–M48) This task focuses on the elements of policy dissemination and interactions with European and national policy- and decision makers, such as EU institutions and national governments, as well as their associated agencies, HTA bodies, health system planners/managers. It contributes to the sustainability of the project, by encouraging the outcomes of the project be taken up by decision-makers and stakeholders. Based on the lessons from the project and the setup of its instrument, a policy recommendations guide will be formulated. Finally, a policy event will thereafter be organized to disseminate these recommendations to a broad audience of international, European and national policy - and decision-makers.

Objectives of WP9 include:

- To develop, implement and update the dissemination and communication plan.
- To carry out all the editorial activities related to the communication and dissemination plan, whilst actively engaging the relevant stakeholders
- To liaise with the existing EU-initiatives, including the Mission on Cancer and the EBCP

- To liaise with representatives and authorities of the EU member states and associate countries in order to implement and exploit the results of the project at National level

WP9 is led by OECI and co-led by ECO with three national umbrella organisations (FAVO, FABC and APOZ) covering Italy, Romania and Bulgaria, carrying out networking activities with cancer patient organizations at European, national, regional and local level to increase the participation of cancer patients on health policymaking. In addition, EAPC with its expertise in dissemination and outreach, policy engagement, palliative care.

3. Communication and Dissemination Objectives

The Communication and Dissemination Plan plays a key role in supporting the project in achieving its objectives. In this respect, this plan sets forth the following objectives:

- **O1:** To increase the visibility of the EUonQoL project and its activities;
- **O2:** To showcase how the project tackles current challenges and its positive impact on society, to attract potential beneficiaries/users of the project results;
- **O3:** To engage with relevant stakeholders, pursuing valorisation of the project activities and outcomes and multi-stakeholder involvement;
- **O4:** To raise awareness about EUonQoL and patient engagement;
- **O5:** To build synergies with other EU-funded projects, foster collaboration, avoid duplication and maximise impact;
- **O6:** To widely disseminate EUonQoL results beyond the Pilot Sites involved in the survey and project consortium.

4. Strategy

The communication and dissemination channels outlined in this CDP are selected to convey key messages and outcomes of the project to the largest possible number of stakeholders and target groups.

This is to maximize the impact of the project at scientific, economic, and societal levels, thus contributing to the goal of the mission on cancer: "to improve the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030, through prevention, cure and for those affected by cancer including their families, to live longer and better".

EUonQoL brings together a well-integrated network of individuals, teams and organisations with expertise across different fields - epidemiologists, oncologists, professionals operating in the fields of palliative medicine and survivorship, psychology, psycho-oncology, behavioral intervention, information and digital technology, privacy, social science, ethic and humanity scientists, as well as health economists and patients' representatives.

They all work applying a comprehensive approach towards a common goal: addressing the needs of cancer patients and survivors.

4.1 Stakeholder Engagement

Good communication is about giving the right information to the right audience at the right time and in the right format. Mapping all the stakeholders and their interest is of capital importance to achieving the EUonQoL’s objectives.

This detailed mapping allows for planning and designing targeted communication for each segment of the target audience from the onset of the project, and iteratively co-developing key messages. In addition, stakeholder engagement is essential to ensure that the EUonQoL-Kit produces data that stakeholders can use to address unmet needs, expectations and preferences of cancer patients and survivors.

Figure 1: EUonQoL | Stakeholder Engagement Plan

Stakeholder involvement is organised by WP2 of the project “Involvement of stakeholders and patients”, as part of Task 2.3 of the EUonQoL Project: “Create and Support Stakeholder Involvement”, led by the European Cancer Organisation. It follows that Figure 1 | Stakeholder Engagement Plan was produced within the scope of D2.2.

Stakeholder engagement will be organised on two levels:

1. A **fixed stakeholder board** including 12 representatives from key actors with different expertise including from medical societies, patient organisations, researchers and policymakers, as well as social workers and other major EU projects on quality of life.

2. **Broader consultation and involvement of stakeholders** from the cancer healthcare, patient and advocacy community. This will be carried out through ECO’s Focused Topics Networks (FTN), as well as ECO’s Patient Advisory Committee (PAC).
3. **Organisation of Stakeholder Fora:** These events will be open to any interested stakeholder and it will serve as a common platform of public engagement for all work packages of the project, rather than separate activities taking place on the different elements of its workplan.

Below is Table 1: EUonQoL | Stakeholder Profile, which outlines the rationale behind the potential profiles of the stakeholders to be involved in the EUonQoL project:

Potential Stakeholders Profile	Stage of Involvement			
	Involved in the early-stage design	Ongoing Co-developers	Users	
			Using the tool	Acting up on the data
Patients, caregivers, specific communities/marginalised groups and their representative/supporting organisations , including grassroot social health organisations	Having their say on what data they are willing to share and what are the gaps when tackling QoL		To give input on their QoL	
Stakeholder organisations involved in QoL advocacy (e.g. patient organisations and support groups, field-specific charities)		Ensuring that the questionnaire is fitted to identify patients needs		To advocate for QoL and support patients how it might be needed
Civil Society Organisations	Identifying social barriers and facilitators to QoL			
Researchers e.g. from academia, public health professionals, from market research organisations..	Input on already existing tools	Data gathering, conducting research and translating research into practice	In charge of collecting the data	Having data to compare QoL at international level
Medical Societies		Ensuring that the questionnaire is aligned with the organisations need and the overall "Beating cancer plan" goals		Using the data to improve their action lines on their specific scope
Policy-makers working on cancer quality of life and care policies (Specific departments in European Commission, national cancer/health authorities)		Envisioning and discussing the opportunities on how evidence-based policy can be improved		Using the data to support health and social policies

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Regulatory authorities and payers (EMA, health insurers, HTA)				Using the data to improve their action lines on their specific scope
Healthcare professionals, services, centres and networks involved in QoL	Early involved as first-hand experiencers		They might be in charge of collecting data	Using the data to improve healthcare practices and methodologies used in practice.
Hospital managers and hospital federations			They might be in charge of collecting data	Ensuring/discussing what/how solutions can be implemented in the field
Chief medical information officers (CMIO)			In charge of processing collected data	
Similar projects & initiatives		Ensuring good alignment of EUonQoL with other major initiatives in the space		

Table 1: EUonQoL | Stakeholder Profile

4.2 Target Audience

The table below provides an outline of the target groups we will aim at through tailored communication & dissemination activities.

Who?	Why?
<p><u>Scientific Target Groups</u> Healthcare: Public, Private, Universities, Scientific Societies And Professional (ESMO; ESO; ESTRO, ESSO, EORTC), Organisations And NGOs (EAPC, ECO, ECPC).</p>	Generate knowledge and evidence to achieve deeper insights into QoL aspects, patient preferences and unmet needs so that health and care systems can better address them thanks to new metrics on QoL.
<p><u>Societal Target Groups</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients, Caregivers and Survivors • Healthcare Providers 	To improve patients' and survivors' QoL and ensure that they can achieve personal and professional goals, including return to work if they wish so, while respecting individual, social and cultural rights and values.
<p><u>Policy Makers/ Regulators</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WHO • EU • National Authorities 	To better understand inequalities in access to care. Additional evidence to consider in the design of labour market and social protection policies that are facilitating return to work and active participation in society.
<p><u>Economic Target Groups</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Labour Market • Social Protection 	To improve regulations to facilitate working conditions & return to work.

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<p>European Citizens at National, Regional and Local Community Levels</p>	<p>Citizen engagement activities to implement the mission on cancer, but as added value to build trustful dialogues with to provide direct feedback from citizens on the EU cancer activities& policies.</p>
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Table 2: EUonQoL | Target Audience

4.3 EUonQoL Visual Identity

The visual identity is at the heart of establishing a coherent and consistent image for the EUonQoL project.

In order to build project visibility across different stakeholders, to raise its presence and awareness, and to ensure consistency throughout the project duration, designing a brand identity of the project, i.e. project’s logo and dissemination templates, is the first dissemination task we was accomplished.

The Logo of the project was agreed upon in M1 of the project, and is described in Figure 2 below:

Concept

The main reference for the design is data collected from a patient and transferred to a common repository. The circles and rectangles evoke the idea of a questionnaire and facilitate the identification and the interpretation of the brand. The use of a gradient energizes the image.

Dimensions

The size of the logo and font can be changed to suit the graphic requirements of the project.

Font

Akrobat Regular
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Akrobat Black
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Colors

49AD40
C=72 M=0 Y=94 K=0

7365AA
C=64 M=64 Y=0 K=0

Gradient

Figure 2: EUonQoL | Logo Description

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4.4 EU Emblem

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

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The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

For the purposes of their obligations, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

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4.5 Online Presence

EUonQoL Website / Restricted Area / OneDrive

Website Link: www.euonqol.eu

The website serves as the first point of contact with the project for a wide audience, presenting its scope, activities and progress. At the same time, it represents the main communication and dissemination channel ensuring the visibility and outreach, regularly updating the audience on activities within the project, but also relevant news, documents and activities related to the topics relevant to EUonQoL. The website will be publicly launched on 30 June 2023.

Work on the website will continue throughout the project, incorporating content as soon as it becomes available. The design of the website is based on the following technical features and characteristics:

- A user-friendly and attractive interface, easy navigation, open to the public of potential users and different stakeholders
- Clear, simple structure, layout with images evoking real everyday life, positive, and encouraging emotions
- Optimised in responsive mode for all types of mobile devices (phones, tablets for both iOS and Android operating systems)
- Fully accessible by all users
- GDPR compliant, including all GDPR-related features (privacy consent for all forms, consent for cookies on a first visit, etc.) *(to be defined)*
- Private area and OneDrive buttons (with access available by authorized users)
- Header with logo and menu – footer with acknowledgement and linked social icon

Website Structure

The website structure will reflect the needs of the project, all work packages and partners while ensuring clear and intuitive navigation. To ensure the provision and information sharing in a consistent and clear manner, the website will include:

- **a password-protected Restricted Area**, which will store final versions of the documents produced by the partners;
- **a OneDrive collaborative area**, dedicated to storing working documents pertinent to the project.

OECI Newsletter

The OECI Newsletter is an online bulletin designed to keep the European Cancer Community informed of the news and current affairs of the Organisation, and to further involve the OECI membership in the Grouping's growth and development. The OECI Mailing List comprises 2,500 contacts including:

- Senior leadership in OECI Membership
- OECI Accreditation & Designation Programme Network
- Prominent cancer stakeholders, including EC contacts, cancer organisations & associations, EC Project mailing lists

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- ▶ OECI will produce a special OECI - EUonQoL edition dedicated to providing a general overview on project activities, news and updates biannually for the entire duration of the project;
 - ▶ News & Updates on the project will be circulated regularly via OECI newsletter, upon necessity, for the entire duration of the project;
 - ▶ The newsletter will be disseminated via Mailchimp to the entire OECI Mailing List.

In addition, WP9 encourages all Consortium partners to brief their audiences on the main challenges and successes of the EUonQoL projects via their own newsletters.

Social Media

The extensive use of social media is aimed at increasing the awareness of potential users, spark interest in the project, and encouraging target groups to take part in project events and download the project's outputs.

Each channel is intended to reach a specific audience, and the messages will be adapted accordingly.

Social media is intended to act as an accelerator of the discussion; different social media channels will trigger snowball/networking effect and enable the project to reach beyond its 'usual suspects' audience. The various Social Media profiles are selected to reach out to a wide and relevant audience.

The content shared on each platform will include different types of outputs and will redirect and feed traffic to the main website. Supporting visual material will be used in different social media channels in order to highlight messages.

In general, appealing visuals will help catch the attention of the followers/audience and invite them to read more and learn more about the proposed topics. For instance, video teasers shared on social media will invite the target audience to watch the full videos. The illustrative elements, such as banners for social media profiles, will help create a brand consistency and a visual identity for the project.

As regards the Social Media platforms to be used, after an internal discussion with WP9 partners during the kickoff meeting of the project, we have decided to focus our efforts on two Social Media platforms – Twitter and LinkedIn.

Twitter

Handle: @EUonQoL

Link: <https://twitter.com/EUonQoL?s=20>

Hashtags: #EUonQoL; #QoL; #reseach #innovation #CancerMission #HorizonEurope
#cancerresearch #PatientEmpowerment ##CancerResearch #GivingVoice2Patients
#LeavingNoCancerPatientBehind

This channel is used for short news flashes, using a clear and crisp style, not too descriptive or institutional. Twitter allows the rapid communication between professionals, organisations and media. It is a real-time communication tool. It allows tweeting questions and having followers respond within several seconds.

Although Twitter is less used in some European regions and on a local level among citizens, it is a major social media network used at the EU level within the European institutions, umbrella organisations and international organisations. Thus, Twitter is mainly used to reach stakeholders at EU level, connect with other relevant projects and initiatives.

Offering only short messages – 280 characters – Twitter is known as a highly paced network demanding frequent activity and updates in order to maintain an active and attractive profile. Retweets enable sharing of interesting content generated by other users as well as the possibility to easily spread messages to a wide audience. We will actively work on the creation of relevant connections that will actively contribute to widening the outreach.

As Twitter is a high-paced social media network, around 3-5 posts will be published per month.

LinkedIn

Group name: EUonQoL

Link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/euongol/>

Hashtags: #EUonQoL; #QoL; #reseach #innovation #CancerMission #HorizonEurope #cancerresearch #PatientEmpowerment ##CancerResearch #GivingVoice2Patients #LeavingNoCancerPatientBehind

Being a social network for professionals, LinkedIn allows the creation of dedicated communities and groups to discuss specific topics and spread information to a wide professional audience. In this sense, a group has been created and used to connect with key stakeholders as well as relevant projects and initiatives to build synergies and foster knowledge transfer.

Selected articles, news pieces and other communications content will also be shared on this platform. Via LinkedIn, EUonQoL will seek to create a community to share experiences, events, studies, news and relevant information with peers.

The frequency of posts published by administrators in the group is foreseen to 1-2 per month.

Social Media Main Contents

The above-mentioned social media channels will be used to maximise the visibility, dissemination and support to the further exploitation process (when possible) of the following content:

- Project objectives, activities and benefits
- Presentation of EUonQoL partners
- Findings from reports and deliverables (storytelling style)
- Present clusters in depth – thematic priorities, commitments, strategies, what they have been doing so far and activities developed within the project
- Presentation of used methodologies and their benefits
- Promotion of EUonQoL events – Local final events and Final conference – What are they about? Why you should not miss them? How can you participate? Who is attending (presentation of speakers)? Join us!
- Sharing videos
- Promotion of webinars

- Interesting news from partners
- Dissemination of public deliverables

In addition, in order to maximize project visibility, WP9 highly recommends all consortium partners to constantly disseminate news on the EUonQoL project on their own social media platforms.

4.6 Other Dissemination Tools

OECI Magazine

The OECI Magazine is an inclusive communication tool designed to promote OECI's mission. The Magazine is an independent source featuring news in the field of cancer; a glimpse behind OECI's running activities, updates on the latest EC actions and additional topics of interest for the whole European cancer community.

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- ▶ OECI will produce one special Edition of the OECI Magazine, exclusively dedicated to the EUonQoL project on M48 of the Project
 - ▶ OECI will include news, articles & updates on the EUonQoL project biannually in the regular OECI Magazine editions

Events

Networks are created, consolidated, and grown by meeting other people. The most effective way to consolidate a network and to align a group's efforts in achieving a mutual goal is by holding internal meetings and events. At the same time, the best way to grow a network is by attending and participating to external events.

They are excellent channels in which to disseminate the EUonQoL project results. WP9 will endeavour to coordinate the involvement of the consortium in related EU forums, workshops, and other events when considered appropriate.

The events to promote the project include, among others:

- The OECI Oncology Days, the main OECI annual event, will host a dedicated session to present the state of play of some of the main projects related to the Mission on Cancer - including EUonQoL - every year throughout the whole duration of the project
- The European Cancer Patient Coalition (ECPC) General Assembly
- A Session at the European Parliament Challenge Cancer Intergroup organised in collaboration with ECPC
- European Association for Palliative Care (EAPC) World Congress

Final conference

The final conference will provide a synthesis of the main policy and practice-oriented findings of the project, serving to increase the visibility of the project, foster the exploitation of results, and present it to the general public, target groups and relevant stakeholders.

The details about the final conference (location, venue, organisation, specific themes and objectives, target audience and participants) will be laid out in a Concept Note to facilitate understanding among partners. The monitoring and coordination of it will be undertaken by an event organisation team, led by OECI but in close cooperation with other partners. The final conference will take place in M48 of the EUonQoL project within the framework of the OECI Oncology Days. It will include an expected attendance of at least 150 participants.

5. Action Plan

The EUonQoL CDP should be understood as a living document. Accordingly, it is planned to publish an updated version to allow it to evolve over time, as a result of new or emerging information and opportunities. This includes a yearly review and a clear communication policy for relevant audiences to target and the appropriate channels to use throughout the project duration. This also includes a communication calendar to be agreed upon and produced in collaboration with WP9 partners.

The dissemination includes communication by means of a public website, forums, public health events, conferences, journals, other publications and engagement with news and social media.

In addition, the project aims to proactively inform and involve the intended user community to increase awareness about integrated palliative care. This will be done in close alignment with all the WPs, as it supports their work (e.g. contacting relevant stakeholders), and also as a way to maximise their impact (e.g. dissemination in social media of academic outputs).

Outreach activities will be designed to foster collaboration with related projects, European Initiatives, Patient and Scientific Organizations/Societies, among others.

Communication and dissemination will be organised by combining face-to-face events with online channels and traditional press strategies.

Table 3 below is an outline of the EUonQoL Communication and Dissemination Strategy over the four years of the project and it encompasses 4 stages, as follows: 1. Building strategy & awareness; 2. Maximising outreach; 3. Solidifying the consolidation of the project results; 4. Ensuring exploitation of the final project outcomes.

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YEAR 1 Strategy & Awareness	YEAR 2 Outreach	YEAR 3 Consolidation	YEAR 4 Exploitation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication & Dissemination Plan - Leaflet - Website - Social Media - OECI Oncology Days - Mission cancer events - Patients/Stakeholder engagement - Focus Group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OECI Oncology Days - Patients/Stakeholder meetings/ focus group - Mission cancer events - Joint workshops - Health Policy Forums - Publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OECI Oncology Days - Mission cancer events - Joint workshops - Health Policy Forums - Patenting Analysis - Publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OECI Oncology Days - Mission cancer events - Joint workshops - Publications - PP agreements - Patenting and exploitation - Final Conference

Table 3: EUonQoL | Communication and Dissemination Strategy

No.	Deliverable Name	Due Date
D9.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan	30 June 2023
D9.2	Project Website	30 June 2023
D9.3	Report on networking activities	30 April 2026
D9.4	Policy recommendation guidelines	30 June 2026
D9.5	Outcomes of communication and engagement	31 December 2026
No.	Milestone Name	Due Date
MS9.1 - M14	Website, email addresses, social media, videoconferencing tool	31 March 2023
MS9.2 - M15	Proceedings of Final conference	30 April 2026

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Table 4: EUonQoL | Project Deliverables & Milestones

6. Quality Control

Sharing results and multiplying impacts requires input and close cooperation with other work packages and project partners.

Whilst OECI and ECO are co-leading WP9, the core communication team also comprises a representative from each WP of the project, who will be collaborating with WP9 on communication and dissemination activities throughout the whole duration of the project.

Guidelines

The Communication and Dissemination Plan aims at providing guidelines for the project partners to ensure consistency in all communication and dissemination activities and high quality of the materials produced within the project. Guidelines intend to provide instructions, templates and recommendations for smooth performance, consistency and efficiency of all communication and dissemination activities and products.

An initial set of templates, guidelines and recommendations are already included in this document. In addition, WP9 will develop further templates and guidelines should the need arise during the implementation of the project.

Open Access

EUonQoL embeds the 8 ambitions on Open Science approach:

- **Open Data** - All data and results will adhere to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). This will facilitate the final process of data export needed from the ICT platform, as well as retrieval of any needed information for further studies / data quality assessment and integration of information coming from heterogeneous sources. This will ensure research communities and health authorities can collaborate effectively and advance the speed of response and further discoveries. EUonQoL will contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) through knowledge and data sharing. This will facilitate the diffusion of the latest information on QoL of cancer patients and survivors.
- **New generation metrics** – EUonQoL will generate a new matrix of metrics which includes clinical, biological, psychological, and social indicators. In this frame, EUonQoL will also contribute to advancing the conventional indicators for research quality and impact, proposing innovative measures. Future of scholarly communication - EUonQoL will provide freely accessible peer-reviewed scientific publications and early sharing of different kinds of research outputs.
- **Rewards** - EUonQoL consortium will contribute to sustain that research career evaluation systems should fully acknowledge open science activities.

- **Research integrity** - EUonQoL will adhere to commonly agreed standards of research integrity, in line with the European code of conduct for RRI and ALLEA. All scientific activities will be based on both personal integrity and ethical responsibilities for research involving human participants, personal data, and artificial intelligence (NLP). Since collaborative research brings about inherent difficulties resulting from complex roles and relationships, common but not necessarily identical interests, management requirements and cultural-disciplinary differences, EUonQoL will be careful on aspects related to data fabrication, scientific falsification and plagiarism, and misuse of funds.
- **Education and skills:** the consortium will contribute to diffuse appropriate knowledge sharing in the field of QoL.
- **Citizen science** – at the core of the EUonQoL there is the adoption of a multi-stakeholder co-design methodology. Citizens and patients involvement is essential to ensure that the EUonQoL-Kit captures the aspects of QoL that matter most to patients, as well as to safeguard that various patient-facing materials in data collection and dissemination are tailored to needs and preferences of patients

KPIs

Regular monitoring and evaluation activities will be conducted to measure gains and successes and provide information about progress with implementation, as well as lessons learned, and thus help revisit the overall objectives so that we do not get side-tracked.

All activities need to be measured and evaluated. The evaluation of qualitative and quantitative performance data gives insights that are needed to:

- optimise the CDP and ongoing activities;
- correct and fine-tune planning;
- make targeting more effective and therefore increase reach;
- improve efficiency and minimise costs.

Data will be collected from the following sources:

- Media monitoring
- Web analytics tools
- Social media analytics tools
- Post-event feedback forms

The EUonQoL KPIs shall be thoroughly monitored and measured on an annual basis. A reviewing process involving all WP9 partners, as well as the EUonQoL Executive Committee will ensure a revision of the KPIs so that they are realistic and relevant, in compliance with the development of the project. It follows that the metrics treated in Table 5 may be subject to variation as a result of the annual revision process, so as to adapt and improve performance and project impact.

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Communication and Dissemination Indicators	
Tool	KPI
Website	600 – 800 visitors per month Countries average: ca. 30 different countries
Social Media	At least 1500 followers on social media platforms
Leaflet	At least 2 at project start and project end
Joint activities events organized with the EC	At Least 4
Specific sessions on EUonQoL at the OECI Oncology Days	4 with at least 200 participants
National patient federations meetings	4 at national level with at least 100 participants
No Dissemination events	At least 50
Lay language publications	At least 10
Joint peer-reviewed publications	At least 20

Table 5: EUonQoL | Communication and Dissemination KPIs

7. Conclusions

This plan defines the communication and dissemination strategy that will be implemented to increase the impact of EUonQoL project. Difficulties and risks might arise along the way due to the fact that EUonQoL project joins several partners from different backgrounds. Also, there might be risks that depend on the performance of different actions. In this section, we try to evaluate those risks before they come in order to set preventing measures.

Risk	Degree of Likelihood	Degree of Severity	Mitigation Measure
Low impact of dissemination activities	Medium	Medium	Review the plan and activities based on KPIs analysis
Low involvement of the partners in communication activities	Medium	Medium	OECI and ECO expertise in the field and development of key messages, communication rules & procedures, tools and

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		<p>events will ensure meeting the KPIs</p>
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Table 6: EUonQoL | Risks and Mitigation Measures

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